

A SURVEY ON CONTINUOUS LINE ILLUSTRATION DEVELOPMENT FROM SKETCHES OR IMAGES

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Abstract—Continuous line illustrations (CLI) consist of a single line in a sketch that is drawn without lifting our drawing aid from the surface until the work is completed. For the given input sketch first, detect the edges, and using this edge we can perform the joining of the curves. After identifying the curves according to their priority they get connected by using some predefined rules and thus obtained the CLI. Even though the area of CLI is not well explored, many researchers are curious about how to discover more features under computer graphics. Most works in this area already have many flaws. To reduce these flaws many methods are developed to develop CLI from sketches and images.

Index Terms—Continuous Line Illustration, edge detection, curve creating, TSP.

I. INTRODUCTION

The art of one-line drawing begins in the early twentieth century. A famous example is drawings made by Pablo Picasso and Leonardo Da Vinci, the line in a continuous line drawing is unbroken from beginning to end. The drawing implement stays in uninterrupted contact with the surface of paper during the entire drawing. Those completed drawings give the effect that they can be unwound. This sort of drawing is considered an exercise, it forces the artist to closely observe the subject and also loosen up the artistic sense. Although the creation of continuous line illustration has been popular among artists, very few works on this kind of drawing can be found in the field of computer graphics. CLI is a drawing consisting of a single line. This technique is commonly taught at the early stages of our artistic senses. These drawing exercises evolve into beautiful works of art. Other than an artistic field, CLI has applications in Quilting designs steel wire sculptures, connect the dot puzzles, etc. as for the work here they are introducing a novel idea for converting an image to CLI, these single lines represent an image that gives a unique charm. Also unintentionally they are using this method of drawing in southern Indian culture that is in Kolam and northern India as Rangoli.

The first thing you should understand is that neither drawing will be flawless. Imperfections will be seen with continuous line drawing. However, it is typically these very flaws

that make the designs so aesthetically appealing. Instead of ignoring the mark's flaws, embrace them and allow them to give character to the final product. The constraints that should be followed by a line to be a CLI are Once you've placed your pen or pencil on the surface, don't take it off until the drawing is finished. Your objective is to describe the subject in a single, concise line. It can thicken and thin in places, but it should never break. Try and move your hand at the same rate that you move your gaze to examine the subject. This will aid in the creation of more precise proportions and forms. But keep in mind that perfection is unattainable. Do not delete. Allow for flaws and allow them to be a human factor in your work. (As humans, we are drawn to items created by other humans.). Make multiple sketches in one sitting and experiment with different tools. For an eager student, these sorts of drawing always will be an asset for his future. It's a great exercise to get motivated and improve the skill of observation of a subject. Quilting is an application of CLI, a project to produce "quiltimation," an animation in which each frame is a quilt, which has spurred the development of automated methods for generating single lines that fill arbitrary regions. They present a walkthrough of the algorithm blanching tool development kit: a 4-step process for creating fills, each of which can be modified to produce different graphical effects[1]. Another method that can automatically create a sewing pattern for an entire duvet from a photo. This technique starts with a segmented image, extracts desired and optional edges, and creates a continuous seam by approximating the rural factor problem (RPP). In addition to many quilt patterns, this provides visual and numerical comparisons with previous single line illustration methods[2].

II. EVOLUTION OF CLI

A Continuous Line Illustration (CLI) is a form of drawing that is made up of only one line. This approach is often taught in schools and many art workshops at their early stages and can aid students to free their artistic sensibilities. In many instances, these easy drawing activities blossom into amazing pieces of art.

A. *Labrynth and mazes*

The "labyrinthine projection" technique Morales entails tracing a single non-intersecting path and generating shade effects by manipulating the number of lines in particular places. In Slater's drawings, a single non-intersecting line spans the whole surface and creating an area with varied width and shade. As a consequence, stunning and vivid works of art are produced. In *Organic Labyrinths and Mazes*[3], they introduced the graphics community to the fascinating field of maze art and introduced a model for the creation of automated organic-looking mazes and mazes. The spiritual labyrinth is a meditative path laid out with careful artistic intent to set you free, while the puzzling maze is a challenging structure designed to trick and entrap. Here their input is a set of curves in a plane. The approach is not ideally suited to structured mazes but the resulting curves can be pushed by forces towards grid lines and then post-processed into a grid maze by selecting the grid cells traversed by the curves. And also embed the algorithm parameters within a general high-level interaction framework, to provide NPR simulation users with greater creative control. Feedback from the game and physical maze designers indicates that interactive programs like ours will allow the creation of richer environments, without sacrificing overall design control. The output patterns also show promise for use in watermarking, image compression, and multi-variable visualization. Our curves have similar properties of good autocorrelation and thus could watermark or compress images by encoding the 1D image stream along with the algorithm parameters and initial curves. The visual effect of multiple texture maps can be quite clear on the curve generated by our algorithm. As a result, our labyrinthine structures may help in the visualization and understanding of multi-variable texture maps.

In *Image-Guided Maze Construction* Jie Xu Craig et al.[4] presented a graphical and combinatorial algorithm for developing mazes that are based on images. The popularity of mazes and labyrinths was rapidly growing in the levels of computer games and puzzles. They take images as input and construct the mazes based on their basic structure and texture. This helps to develop nonintersecting mazes rather than intersecting lines in continuous line illustrations. This led to the development of CLIs in the future. Even in the early era, some labyrinth habits of the domestic pigeon[5] were studied by Walter S Hunter from the Psychological Laboratory of the University of Texas. That explains about analysis of the labyrinth habits of the domestic pigeon to further the solution to some questions. *Rectangular Maze Construction by Combining Algorithms and Designed Graph Patterns*[6], in this work Dr. Wen-Shou Chou explains how digital mazes can be constructed automatically related to some algorithms. In [7] the researchers generated a CLI from an image through the use of image processing techniques and the application of concepts in graph theory. They extract the edges of the image and create a graph based on them. At this point, the graph undergoes a series of modifications, and

then a path that traverses all of its edges is found. This path is then transformed into a CLI after several post-processing operations. Depending on the application, users might find a lack or excess of details in the resulting CLI. A few examples are: controlling the amount of dots in connect-the-dots puzzles and changing the amount of detail in the CLI according to the distance from the viewer. For this reason, they have also incorporated a method for allowing users to specify levels of detail in the final illustration while maintaining the coherence of the CLI between detail levels at the same time. In short, our approach takes an image I and the desired number of detail levels n as input, and do the following, extract the contours of the input image, classify the contours into n detail levels, infer a graph from the extracted contours, find a path that traverses through all graph edges, trace a continuous line based on the obtained path and the specified detail level. This technique is constrained by the present state of edge detection algorithms, which are susceptible to line sub-detection and over-detection. Even with the level-of-depth technique, this results in line congestion in some places of the graphic and a lack of information in others. They want to expand on this work by using visual attention factors to determine which parts should be included in the continuous line image. They are also focusing on enhancing the visualization of these drawings by introducing new effects such as darkening certain regions by adjusting the density of line segments, altering line width at specific points, and line haloing. Mazes and labyrinths have been found in ancient and modern human cultures throughout history. From the Cretan and Egyptian labyrinths to the mazes seen in today's newspapers and weekly magazines, it is evident that mazes are and have always been an important part of our civilization. Mazes have also found their way into the creative world, appearing in the works of Morales, Christopher Berg, and others, transforming them into conceptual instruments for conveying sentiments and ideas. Fernando J. Wong and Shigeo Takahashi[8] presented an approach to automation to create a maze from a given image taking into account its most important characteristics and the direction of its edges. Although there are many maze creation programs, most of them create mazes based on squares. This simple approach can instantly generate mazes of varying difficulty, however, the ability to express is quite limited and much depends on the skill of the artist. The technology contribution here is to fully automate the maze creation process processed by combining the inherent flow characteristics of image samples provided while retaining the associated maze aesthetic but stimulating. They also focused on a specific type of labyrinth that has reached a high level of popularity in recent years, called the Visual Maze, which is characterized by an object or the image revealed after solving the maze. The second technical contribution lies in the equipment of our maze with this trait to make them more attractive to the maze handler. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first attempt to integrate two different picture patterns in a single maze it is like a hybrid maze. For maze bilateral filter is used for smoothening the image. And based on this an edge tangent

flow field is proposed that will help to obtain a vector field oriented in the edge direction. The most significant edge is extracted with FDOG (Flow-Based Difference Of Gaussian) filter. The produced contour is taken as well. Then apply the line thinning algorithm to get a uniform line segment from extracted edges. Cubic interpolation is done for smoothening and thinning. In direction of the vector field taking the red lines as reference, a set of streamlines is drawn. Then maze grid is made tracing the streamlines perpendicular to the vector field. As for the solution path, secondary image contour is extracted. From the intersection of the previously generated grid, a cell sequence is generated. The vicinity of sequences is filled and a binarized version of the secondary image is obtained. Then the cells corresponding to this binarized image are also filled. In this filled region do the Delaunay triangulation, based on short distance these lines get merged. Merging causes the whole structure to have a starting and ending point. Thus the solution is obtained. Although results achieve high image quality for a large group of images, they still lack the level of detail found in labyrinths by Christopher Berg and other maze designers. The proposed solution pipeline generation process can be incorporated into other maze- building approaches such as fine, as long as they can provide a previously generated grid. Another possible extension would be the creation of measure-compatible images to automate the mixed mazes image selection process. Also want to explore the applicability of current approaches to other problems, such as continuous line illustration. developing mazes that are based on images. The popularity of mazes and labyrinths was rapidly growing in the levels of computer games and puzzles. They take images as input and construct the mazes based on their basic structure and texture. This helps to develop nonintersecting mazes rather than intersecting lines in continuous line illustrations. This lead to the development of CLIs in the future. Even in the early era, some labyrinth habits of the domestic pigeon[5] were studied by Walter S Hunter from the Psychological Laboratory of the University of Texas. That explains about analysis of the labyrinth habits of the domestic pigeon to further the solution to some questions. Rectangular Maze Construction by Combining Algorithms and Designed Graph Patterns[6], in this work Dr. Wen-Shou Chou explains how digital mazes can be constructed automatically related to some algorithms. In [7] the researchers generate a CLI from an image through the use of image processing techniques and the application of concepts in graph theory. They extract the edges of the image and create a graph based on them. At this point, the graph undergoes a series of modifications, and then a path that traverses all of its edges is found. This path is then transformed into a CLI after several post-processing operations. Depending on the application, users might find a lack or excess of details in the resulting CLI. A few examples are: controlling the amount of dots in connect-the-dots puzzles and changing the amount of detail in the CLI according to the distance from the viewer. For this reason, they have also incorporated a method for allowing users to specify levels of detail in the final illustration while maintaining the coherence

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B. TSP

Continuous line drawings via the traveling salesman problem[9], here Robert Bosch, Adrienne Herman follows some to obtain continuous line illustration of a picture. First, they try to resize the target picture and convert it to a portable grey map where each pixel has a specific pixel value between 0 and 255. The second step is to divide the picture into squares. Then construct and solve the TSP. Like this paper, many areas are using the TSP method for different processes. But still, there are better methods to use instead of TSP because TSP is a time-consuming process. Bosch and Herman describe detailed how to use TSP in different ways for constructing a CLI. They use the city distribution method for this. There are various methods like Halftoning, grid-based methods, stippling, dithering, etc.

1) *Halftoning*: Halftoning is a method of breaking images into a set of dots to create the full tone range of a photo. As an example, in printing a black and white photograph in a newspaper here two visible colors are black and white. This will give an illusion of continuous shades of grey. Halftone's main goal is to make the displayed image as close to the image as possible original when viewed from a distance. However, over time, the halftone function is sometimes overloaded with addicts the ultimate goal of stylized rendering: blending artistic touches with rendered images, embedded in the raster part. Pnueli and Bruckstein described a halftone pattern common to all functional dithering algorithms like "Local density of black elements must be proportional to the local grayscale of the original image" [Pnueli and Bruckstein 1996]. Bosch and Herman introduced the notion of TSP art and presented a simple grid-based algorithm for distributing cities in a TSP instance [9]. Artistic Screening[10] is one example where small user-defined shapes take the place of the simple dots usually used in halftoning. Multicolor dither is a generalization of dither mode standard density. Combine with tetrahedral separation, multicolor dither make may have to printed images including a

non-standard ink set. Unlike most previous-dithering methods, the multi-color dither by design ensures that the different base colors selected are printed side by side. Multicolor dither is applied to produce colored images where screen dots are facts out of art.

2) *Stippling*: In Modular Line-Based Halftoning via Recursive Division, Abdalla G. M[11], Ahmed combined generating of stippling points with the plotting of lines. These are combined by using a fast approving algorithm for generating stipple points, they divide the image to equal size by placing several dots in each slice that are proportional to total darkness, ie, mass. Initially, the vertices of corners of the image are taken. When considering the edge that divides the rectangular image into two rectangles so that the mass is equal. Add the endpoints of edges to the vertices. other than this method they help to describe different ways of using halftoning. A) loops- The essence of the fact that every vertex in V is a shared angle is between exactly 2 rectangles in Risk only if we draw 2 parallel sides from each rectangle of R do we obtain closed loops without division. An exception occurs for the 4 rectangles in the corners of the printing, but we can attach the bottom manually, physically, or logically left corner, e.g. in the upper left corner and the lower right corner top right and we've closed loops everywhere. From the edges of a rectangle overlapping the edges of other rectangles, a line Future applications of this idea will create something similar to a halftone with an edge. B) Knots- rather than joining vertices inside the rectangle, join the opposite vertices diagonally. Together these points give an illusion that is under passing each other and also they make curves and bents over vertices and between rectangles, which help to view the structure as knotted loops. To make improvements on this they also consider creating rings and free ends. C) Spanning trees - It is possible to switch from the dots generated to one MST algorithm and produces output similar to that described by Inoue and Urahama [12], but after taking care section, notice that the topology of the vertices and the rectangle provides an inherent mechanism for constructing spanning trees (STs). There is some room for tuning this style to emulate MST Halftoning of Inoue and Urahama, but there are intrinsic limitations. For example, vertices in our trees have a maximum of three connected edges. One possible avenue for future research is to improve the recursive core division algorithm itself. dividing horizontally and vertically is the simplest and easiest and the required color study. Adjust input images for fully automatic processing. Another one is to improve the rendering styles presented here or study the possibility of finding new ones. In Truchet curves and surfaces[13], Cameron Browne, says about Sometimes you want to fill an area with a specific shape with a single unbroken curve. This is possible for practical reasons, such as path planning for automatic embroidery equipment, or purely artistic reasons. Truchet sketch provided a convenient and attractive way to achieve this score. Halftone with the buttons can also be adjusted to build mazes, build on the idea that there are always 4 empty ends in the corners, but it's a hard cult for tracing connected people. For beat halftones Referring

to the tree, the choice of reference vertices can serve as the key to combining maze building. Therefore, the contribution of this article is to enrich the material with four ideas to build mazes with visual instructions that can, for example, be used amply, in the labyrinthine library of the developed combinatorial system by Xu and Kaplan [4]. Seen from an artist's perspective covers a page with small ink dots, this distribution is nothing more than a strangulation technique. Artists and illustrators have used stippling for more than a century to suggest a continuous tone with single ink color. Since the grid-based point distribution is just a dotted line, it seems natural to wonder if its different dashed algorithms can generate compelling TSP versions.[14]. Second's weighted Voronoi stippling[15] is fast and automatic, and produces high-quality stippling drawings. It starts from the original point distribution and improves it using an iterative relaxation process. With every step during iteration, it computes the Voronoi histogram of the points and moves each point to the center of mass of his Voronoi region. The tone of the source image is used to assign an uneven volume to the space, causing dots to move to darker parts of the image. Since the grid-based method distributes the points evenly, it makes for unattractive drawings. There is no control over the distances of points from their nearest neighbors. Close points produce short, jagged edges in the TSP tour. The relaxation algorithm used in the weighted Voronoi dotted line will tend to space the dots as evenly as possible while approaching the tone of the image. This technique avoids the short edges produced in the grid-based approach of TSP. And also a few cities are needed with stippling than the grid-based method to obtain the drawings with better quality.

3) *Dithering*: By fixing a specific pattern for arranging cities very different way of line drawing is obtained for this purpose dithering is a better option. Simply we can say that dithering is a simple form of halftoning and also a specialized form of stippling. Rendering is the final step once the cities are placed, then rendering the path for TSP is selected[14]. An automatic edge enhancement process that works in conjunction with clustered dot dithering. The purpose is not to make the weak edges more visible, but to make the strong edges of the halftone image cleaner looking than and looking more natural. threshold values, which resulted in a compromise of gray level resolution gave spatial resolution improved of neighborhoods of the edges. The rule-based compensation scheme was used to identify and eliminate potentially objectionable pixel patterns caused by threshold changes. Test results show that our method is successful in improving the rendering of text, line art, and natural scenes rendered by cluster dithering. They help to enhance edges for clustered dots and as the result, they produce sharper-edged images, text, etc.[16].

III. EDGE DETECTION

Edge detection includes many mathematical methods to identify edges, and curves in digital images where the brightness of the image changes suddenly or more formally, showing

discontinuity. We can also say that abrupt changes of discontinuity in an image are called edges. Most of the shape information in an image is surrounded by edges. So we first detect these edges in an image and by using these filters and then enhancing the areas of the image that contain the edges the sharpness of the image will increase and The picture will become clearer. Some types of edge detectors, especially stepping edge detectors, are an essential part of many computer vision systems. serving edge detection simplifies image analysis by drastically reducing the amount of data to process while preserving useful structural information about object boundaries. There is certainly a great variety in edge detection applications, but it is believed that many Applications share a common set of requirements. These requirements lead to an abstract edge detection problem, the solution can be applied in any original Problem area. In A Computational Approach to Edge Detection[17], JOHN CANNY describes a technique for the design of edge detectors for arbitrary edge profiles which is based on the specification of detection and localization criteria in a maths form. Let us mention here some specific applications. The BinfordHorn line finder [18] used the edge finder output as input to a program that could isolate simple geometric solids. More recently, model- based vision The ACRONYM system [19] uses an edge detector as an edge end a complex accreditation program. Make of motion [20], [21] can be used to infer the structure of a three-dimensional object from side motion turns or edge points in the image plane. Multiple Modems stereoscopic theory assumes that the image is preprocessed by an edge detector before performing the matching [22], [23]. Beattie [24] describes an edge-based labeling scheme for low-level image understanding. Some novel methods have been proposed for the extraction of three-dimensional information from the contours of the image, namely the shape from the contour [25] and the shape from the texture [26]. Theory Of Edge Detection [27] by D. Marr and E. Hildreth, explained edge detection is done by using intensity variation. Intensity changes in images arise from surface discontinuities and these have the property that they are spatially localized.

IV. CONTINUOUS LINE ILLUSTRATION

Continuous Line Illustration (CLI) is an art style for drawing continuous with a single line. Artists and researchers are both interested in the topic and have proposed different terms of rhythm for drawing CLI. In the computer literature, Bosch and Herman [9] suggested drawing an online automatically by solving the problem of the traveling salesman and the output current density as a function of the luminance of the input image. Wong and Takahashi [7] also suggested outlining the input image using a continuous line. They propose a graphical approach based on Fleury's algorithm to find an eulerian route that goes through all edges in the graph. On the other hand, in the field of art and design, artists [F. Kurnia and J. Chia. The work of Fajar Jeremy, created many striking paintings with concentric circles in the marker that cannot be deleted. Dithering, Stippling, grid-based, etc. are used for finding the

CLIs inside the TSP [14]. In Continuous line drawings via the traveling salesman problem, researchers consider CLI as an optimization problem so they can use TSP for solving the problem. Jie Xu and Craig S. Kaplan proposed a set of combinatorial, graphical algorithms for making mazes from images and these sorts of mazes can be considered as CLIs so that they can find a solution path for the same [14]. While generating picture mazes from black and white images and solutions for the mazes fill up the black pixels. These solutions can be formed like a CLI and can be said to be a CLI formation method [28]. A hierarchical approach to designing continuous line illustrations, drawings consisting of a single line, is presented throughout in Hierarchical Design of Continuous Line Illustrations a work done by Fernando J. Wong and Shigeo Takahashi[29]. The user specifies a graphic that guides the overall shape of the line artwork and proceeds to assign a series of subgraphs to some of its vertices. A line illustration can then be generated by taking into account all these graphs, which can produce complex drawings consisting of several objects. This approach also allows us to maintain the overall structure and direction of the line when graphics are inserted or removed from the illustration. [7] presents a method to automatically generate continuous line illustrations, drawings consisting of a single line, from a given input image. This approach starts by deducing a graph from a set of edges extracted from the image in question and obtaining a path that passes through all the edges of the said graph. The resulting path then undergoes a series of post-processing operations to turn it into a continuous line drawing. Abstracting images into a Continuous-line artistic style[30] focuses on designing and creating illustrations that represent a certain scene with a non-intersecting line. In this approach, the user partitions the image into regions, assigning a style or style to each region. A mesh is then created on the drawing space, according to the parameters specified for each region. The artwork is then obtained as a path that covers most of the area of the mesh. Unlike previous work, our approach allows the user to control the overall flow of a line within a given region, by providing a means to define a tensor field per region of direct influence. to the direction of the road. An Efficient Algorithm for Continuous Line Illustration With Concentric Circles [31], explains an efficient algorithm for automatically creating a single line and a continuous line desire gives an input image. Method of recommending you use concentric circles, to sum up, the algorithm's continuous line illustration. A variety of pre-processing and posting Processing operations have been applied to reflect the intensity of the color city of the input image. An algorithm that constructs the CLD automatically[32], with tone and structural information obtained from the input image. The line connection is maintained by a tree created by path finding taking into account the key characteristics of a given image. The branching tree structure is gradually developed by selecting pixels according to the cost function, linking both tone maps and importance maps. After labeling each branch, an artificial wall was then constructed using a two-step label transfer process to create a unique boundary,

interpreted as the final CLD. The problem of generating the final image that includes a closed curve that does not intersect is a problem. Previously, the CLD art algorithm was created by solving the traveling salesman problem (TSP) (Bosch Herman,2004) once and only once, before returning to the original location.

V. CURVES CREATION

A curve is a line that curves and changes direction gradually. They can be simply wavy or spiral. These lines convey a feeling of comfort and ease, as well as a sensual quality as they remind us of the human body. Circles, ellipses, parabolas, and hyperbolas, as well as arcs, arcs, and segments, are two-dimensional curved shapes. While shapes such as spheres, cylinders, and cones are known as three-dimensional curved shapes. The curve is a set of infinitely large points. Every point has two neighbors except the endpoints. Curves can be broadly classified into three categories explicit, implicit, and parametric curves. Implicit curve representations define the set of points on a curve by employing a procedure that can test to see if a point in on the curve. The explicit representation is not general, since it cannot represent vertical lines and is also single valued. Curves having parametric form are called parametric curves. The explicit and implicit curve representations can be used only when the function is known. Spline Curves in Computer Graphics are piecewise polynomial curves. It is very useful in many applications. Spline curves are used to create animation paths. We use Spline curves to create the model of automobile bodies and other drawings and fonts. It is actually a freeform curve. We define curves with the help of some points. These points are control points. Then we join these control points. (Remember the childhood activity join the dots and guess the picture). There are two approaches for joining these points. If the curve passes through each and every control point then it is Interpolation Spline. However, for Approximate Distance, it does not need to touch any or all control points. The control points define the basic shape of the curve. We can move or manipulate the curves using these control points.[38]

The spline curve is a mathematical representation that is easily constructed an interface that allows the user to design and control the shape of complexes curves and surfaces. The general method is that the user enters a string points and a curve is constructed whose shape follows this sequence. The points are called control points. A curve actually passes through each the control point is called the interpolation curve; a curve passes near The control points but not necessarily through them are called approximation curves.[39]

String art, which uses straight lines to create curves, is well related to the basics of calculus, where an algorithm that finds any tangent on a curve can be computed (integral) and the area below the curve can be determined by adding an infinite number of rectangles, including of course straight lines, formed under a curve (derivative). Once the concept of using nets is understood, threading art can be made two dimensional using paper and crayons or three dimensional

using wooden dowels or straws and embroidery thread or any other. String art also became important to computer design and engineering as it used Be'zier and Castejau's laws to create the illusion of curves from straight lines. Paul de Castejau, a French mathematician and physicist invented the algorithm that Pierre Be'zier used. Pierre Be'zier, a famous inventor, engineer and mathematician invented the "Bezier" curve to describe any coordinate point on a curve[40].

VI. CONCLUSION

This survey paper gives a brief idea of CLI and how it emerges, how it is still has a great role in the graphical world. The single line drawings help the newbies to broaden their sense of drawing. So drawing a CLI help us to loosen up and make the mistakes to a better output. Mostly used method to complete this was by TSP, but that is a time consuming expensive process, so researchers are exploring this area to get a better method to do the same.

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